

Serbian Biochemical Society

President: Marija Gavrović-Jankulović

Vice-president: Suzana Jovanović-Šanta

General Secretary: Jelica Milošević

Treasurer: Milica Popović

Organization Committee

Vladimir Mihailović

Aleksandar Ostojić

Nevena Đukić

Jelena S. Katanić Stanković

Marko Živanović

Nikola Srečković

Stefan Marković

Sladana Đorđević

Nataša Simin

Milan Nikolić

Milica Popović

Jelica Milošević

Scientific Board

Marija Gavrović-Jankulović

Suzana Jovanović-Šanta

Marina Mitrović

Tatjana Jevtović Stoimenov

Ivan Spasojević

Snežana Marković

Melita Vidaković

Natalija Polović

Aleksandra Zeljković

Romana Masnikosa

Radivoje Prodanović

Proceedings

Editor: Ivan Spasojević

Technical support: Dragana Robajac

Cover design: Zoran Beloševac

Publisher: Faculty of Chemistry, Serbian Biochemical Society

Printed by: Colorgrafx, Belgrade

Serbian Biochemical Society

Tenth Conference

with international participation

24.09.2021. Kragujevac, Serbia

“Biochemical Insights into Molecular Mechanisms”

Glioblastoma-associated microglia as a new target and strategy to fight with

Jovana Drljača^{1*}, Dragica Bulajić¹, Aleksandra Popović², Tihomir Dugandžija³, Nebojša Stilinović⁴, Aleksandra Isaković⁵, Slobodan Sekulić⁶, Ivan Čapo⁷

¹*Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad; Serbia*

²*Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

³*Department of Epidemiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

⁴*Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

⁵*Institute of Medical and Clinical Biochemistry, School of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Belgrade; Serbia*

⁶*Department of Neurology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

⁷*Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

**e-mail: jovana.drljaca@uns.ac.rs*

Glioblastoma (GBM) is one of the deadliest primary brain tumors, heavily infiltrated with tumor-associated microglia/macrophages (TAM), which has received a great deal of interest. Due to the negligible number of peripheral macrophages by the 14th day, in our study TAM were referred to as microglia. We evaluated histopathological characterization of TAM and kinetics of their infiltration in U87 orthotopic GBM in immunosuppressed Wistar rats, a commonly used model in preclinical research. To mimic different stages of GBM growth, we evaluated three-time points. Our data showed that the highest areal density of TAM was 7 days after GBM inoculation, with ability to proliferate early after initiation of GBM growth. The areal density of TAM within the tumor correlated with GBM growth and proliferation. Moreover, microglia underwent substantial morphological changes upon exposure to GBM cells. A transition from ramified morphology in peritumoral area to amoeboid shape with larger soma and shortened, thick branches in the tumor core was observed. Higher areal fraction of blood vessels also correlated with the areal density of TAM. Given these pro-invasive features of microglia, this GBM model represents a good basis for further testing of microglia as a target for treatment.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia, Grant No: 142-451-3176/2020-01 and Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (Grant Nos: 175006 and 41025).